

Business Intelligence and Sustainability of Financial Institutions in Nigeria

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This study ascertained the association between business intelligence and sustainability of financial institutions in Nigeria. Two hypotheses were developed for this study. A cross-sectional survey research design was employed. The study population comprised management staff selected from ten (10) different financial institutions in Nigeria with offices in Rivers State. The accessible population comprise of one hundred and thirty-five (135) management staff selected from various financial institutions which includes deposit money banks, insurance firms, and micro finance banks. The study employed a random sampling technique to select the samples. The Taro Yamane formula was used to determine a sample size of 101 from a population of 135. Data were collected through a well-structured questionnaire, with 81 responses successfully retrieved and analyzed. Hypotheses were tested using the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient. The results revealed a strong positive relationship between data warehousing and environmental sustainability, as well as a significant positive relationship between data visualization and environmental sustainability in financial institutions in Nigeria. In conclusion, both data warehousing and data visualization positively impact environmental sustainability. Therefore, it is recommended that financial institutions adopt advanced data visualization tools to simplify complex data and invest in modern data warehousing technologies to enhance sustainability efforts

Keywords: Business Sustainability; Data Warehouse; Data visualization; Sustainability; Environmental Sustainability.

INTRODUCTION

Financial institutions contribute to economic growth by facilitating capital flow and stimulating investment. They are also essential in managing and reducing financial risks. As key players in the financial sector, they influence the development of sustainable economic systems, impact various industries and business operations, and play a vital role in safeguarding human rights and environmental protection worldwide (PWC, 2022).

It is often believed that governments should take the lead in promoting sustainable development, which is why financial institutions have downplayed their own potential contributions to the cause. At first glance, it may seem like the financial markets' focus on short-term gains and the humanitarian, long-term goals of sustainable

development couldn't be more different (European Commission, 1997). However, their perspective has frequently shifted towards viewing environmental concerns as incidental to their business. However, organizations are becoming increasingly aware of the growing pressure to embrace sustainability and are showing greater interest in voluntarily engaging with stakeholders regarding their sustainability initiatives (Haupt, Scholtz, & Calitz, 2015).

Every nation now has sustainability initiatives in place to assist their economies satisfy present requirements without compromising their capacity to fulfil the needs of future generations. A growing number of businesses and organisations, including banks, are committing to long-term sustainability by focussing on profit, planet, and people. By incorporating SDGs into their corporate culture, leadership, strategy, and operations, financial institutions play an essential role in achieving sustainable

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development goals over the long run. A study by Rwakiseta (2018) found that the success or failure of financial institutions may have an impact on society in two ways. Elsayah (2022) argues that the environment and economy, where sector participants conduct their daily activities, have a direct impact. On the other hand, the services and products offered by banks to clients have an indirect effect.

If sustainability programs and efforts are not included into the corporate business plan, then good sustainability performance will not be realized. In 1983, the United Nations convened the Brundtland Commission, formerly known as the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED), to address mounting concerns about the rapid depletion of natural resources caused by economic and social development. The commission's work brought about a generally recognized definition of sustainability. "Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" (U.N., 1987 as cited in Dale, Luke & John, 2011) emphasized the significance of a fair and balanced approach to economic, social, and environmental concerns, as well as the necessity of responsible business practices, in relation to both immediate and long-term goals.

Discover, develop, or create new strategic sustainability decision possibilities with the use of Business Intelligence (BI) technology. These systems can manage vast volumes of data, both organised and unstructured. Consequently, Business Intelligence (BI) development is defined by technologies that are specifically designed to collect, process, and load heterogeneous data from many sources into a single data warehouse. Online analytical processing (OLAP), balanced scorecard, data/text mining, and other similar techniques might also make use of these technologies to visually represent and analyse data descriptively. Furthermore, according to Haupt et al. (2015), business intelligence (BI) can help in overcoming these obstacles and efficiently managing sustainability information. (Mohammed and Nada, Menaouer (2012)

Several corporate decision-making processes are being supported by business intelligence (BI) frameworks, according to Boyer et al. (2010) and Farver (2013). All things considered, the three cornerstones of a business intelligence framework are performance management, enterprise reporting, and business analysis (Muntean, 2018).

With the addition of a sustainability factor, any BI/BA method may be enhanced to better assist performance management by assessing the effort put into this area. A standard business intelligence schema may be enhanced by including the sustainability view through the use of measurements and dimensions reengineering. The purpose of this research is to draw conclusions about the connection between BI and the long-term viability of financial institutions in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Risks associated with the businesses whose operations financial institutions choose to support are inherent to these organisations. To provide just one example, oil and gas activities are notoriously risky and capital expensive. Oil and gas businesses' activities entail dangers to the environment, including pollution, greenhouse gas emissions, and spills. This puts their financing providers at risk of losing investments due to these negative consequences. (Iwolabi and Nwobu, 2017)

The integration of sustainability into the basic operations of financial institutions is a key problem that they confront today. Many banks still have a long way to go before they can successfully embrace and execute sustainable practices, even though this is becoming more important for the long-term health of the economy, the environment, and society. Inadequate data management, disjointed decision-making procedures, and the failure to extract useful insights from massive data sets are common causes of this problem. More openness and responsibility in sustainability reporting is also being demanded by stakeholders, authorities, and customers (Chen, Chiang & Storey, 2012)

Financial institutions are unable to make well-informed judgments due to the absence of efficient systems and tools for managing and analyzing data linked to sustainability. Their operational efficiency, regulatory compliance, sustainability performance, and reputation are all negatively impacted by this gap. In light of the aforementioned issue, the purpose of this research is to investigate how financial institutions in Nigeria could benefit from business intelligence in order to ensure their long-term viability.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The overarching goal of this research is to identify any connections between business intelligence and sustainability of financial institutions in Nigeria. Specifically, this study intends to:

1. Establish the relationship between data warehousing and environmental sustainability of financial institutions in Nigeria
2. Examine the relationship between data visualization and environmental sustainability of financial institutions in Nigeria

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between data warehousing and environmental sustainability of financial institutions in Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between data visualization and environmental sustainability of financial institutions in Nigeria.

Conceptual Framework

Source: Alm and Malmberg (2022); Menaouer, Mohammed and Nada (2022)

Business Intelligence (BI)

When Scott Morton first proposed the idea of a decision support system in 1971, BI was an updated version of his initial notion. Business Intelligence (BI) shifted its focus to analytics in the early 2000s, when it was formally named Business Analytics (BA) in academic circles. When it comes to datasets used to derive meaning from organisational performances and discover new information, BA takes a more open approach, with an emphasis on mathematical and statistical insights (Davenport, 2006). Paradza and Daramola (2021) found that BA places equal emphasis on reporting and future prediction, in contrast to BI's reporting-centric strategy.

According to the consensus among the experts, Business Intelligence (BI) encompasses all the processes, tools, and resources that are necessary to gather, analyze, and display company data in order to back up tactical and strategic decisions (Kimball & Ross, 2016). According to Sabri et al. (2017), there are two main approaches to business intelligence: one is system-oriented, which involves collecting, storing, and presenting data using various tools; the other is process-oriented, which requires users to have some expertise. The following step, after data presentation and process collection, is to make the data analyzable for end users. Business Intelligence (BI) is defined by Dedić and Stanier (2016) as the integration of all the processes, tools, and resources required to gather, evaluate, and display company data in order to facilitate tactical and strategic decision-making (Menaouer, Mohammed & Nada, 2022).

Decision-makers at every level of an organisation can now access, comprehend, analyse, collaborate, and act on information more quickly and simply because to BI's simplification of information discovery and analysis. BI facilitates the transition from information consumption to the development of comprehensive contextual knowledge regarding that data. Organisations may acquire a competitive edge by integrating strategy with

measurements. This allows for quicker, better decision-making across the board. The capacity to turn raw data into useful, actionable insights is known as business intelligence (BI). Businesses may benefit greatly from actionable insights provided by a well-executed BI strategy. Better, more confident choices are made faster with the aid of BI systems. The firm's strengths are recognized and maximized, marketing efforts are shortened, customer connections are improved, efforts are aligned with the firm's plan, and revenues and profits are increased (Mohamed, 2020)

Data Warehousing (DW)

Devlin and Murphy were the first to present the Data Warehouse (DW) (1998). León and Munoz (2021) state that a DW is a read-only database that was specifically made to hold operational history data. It provides users with the ability to query and search for the information they need for decision support and analysis.

According to Han et al. (2011), data warehouses consolidate information from a variety of sources, both internal and external. One of the main functions of a data warehouse is to consolidate several sources of information into one place for the purpose of doing business analytics. To aid in decision-making, a data warehouse compiles subject-oriented, integrated, non-volatile, and time-variant data (Inmon, 2005). A data warehouse, according to Kimball et al. (2008), is an integrated copy of transactional data that has been arranged to optimize data analysis, reporting, and querying. Database warehouses are built to store large amounts of data that may be used to power various applications, such as basic reporting and querying tools and more advanced systems that fall under the umbrella of business intelligence tools. Data mining, online analytical processing, decision support systems, and executive information systems are all examples of such tools (Grey & Watson, 1998). DWs also facilitate and

support a number of ongoing strategic projects, including supply chain management, business performance management (BPM), and customer relationship management (CRM) (Ariyachandra & Watson, 2010).

The process of data extraction, transformation, and loading into data repositories is facilitated by DW technology. Users and decision-support apps are then granted access to the data. Ariyachandra and Watson (2010) suggest that it serves as a data infrastructure for decision support that is put to use for a wide range of decision support tasks.

Data Visualization

Information may be more readily understood by end users via data visualisation, which involves the act of visually representing data (Kumar & Belwal, 2017; Kariyawasam et al. 2021). Graphical displays known as dashboards let users to see data in a comprehensive and visually appealing format, which was considered vital during the field's early stages of development (Alm & Malmberg, 2022).

In a nutshell, visualising anything involves using a mix of visual components (shapes) and variables (colour, locations, etc.) to create an actual, tangible mental picture that can be seen with the naked eye. Some examples of observable realities include people, places, and things in nature; others include the earth's core, blood, and the universe; still others include the wind, air, heat, electrons, sound, and smell; and finally, abstract realities include things like data, ideas, hierarchies, processes, and relationships (Zheng, 2018).

No matter the amount, format (structured or unstructured), or source of the data, data visualization allows for its visual and interactive study and graphical depiction. Data visualization serves multiple purposes, including but not limited to: enhancing analysis and decision support, information seeking, browsing, and navigation; expressing and appreciating artistic beauty; supporting information behaviour; and, of course, having fun or telling stories.

Sustainability

Many discussions have been ignited on the topics of sustainability and sustainable development in many academic fields, corporate settings, and government agencies. In response to sustainability discussions in economics, companies began to prioritise the issue, which led to the development and implementation of new accounting and auditing standards (Alm & Malmberg, 2022).

When looking at global trends during the last decade, the idea of sustainability stands out as one of the most significant. A similar point is made by (Porter & Kramer, 2011), who stress the significance of sustainability in bridging the gap between businesses and the

communities in which they operate. In fact, they say that there should be a drive towards establishing shared value between the firm and the community within which it works. UNWTO defines Sustainable tourism as "tourism that takes full account of its current and future economic, social, and environmental impacts, addressing the needs of visitors, the industry, and the environment and host communities" (UNEP & UNWTO, 2005).

Business Sustainability Reporting (BSR) is a strategy of defining, categorising, measuring, recognizing, and reporting activities for all areas included in Business Sustainability Performance (BSP), thus, enabling enterprises to design and execute their plans (Elsayah, 2022). Sustainable companies are thus capable of optimising their market value in the short, medium, and long term by managing knowledge and every form of economic, social, and environmental challenges (Adams, 2013; Analytics, 2010).

Environmental Sustainability

The environmental business sector comprises of enterprises ranging from established environmental sectors, such as trash management, to emergent "green" pioneers, such as renewable energy and eco-tourism. They have a significant role to play in achieving sustainable development and hence ensuring that they have access to private sector capital is important.

Several research data suggest that unsustainable socio-economic development activities cause a mass amount of environmental harm. The natural environment is degrading in several ways: omission of carbon dioxide (CO₂), producing all types of pollution around us, over-consuming natural resources, cutting forests, deforestation, wildlife and biodiversity loss, droughts, heat waves, floods, rising sea levels, and food insecurity (Ziaul & Shuwei, 2022).

Choosing and doing things in a way that helps the natural world remain habitable for future generations is what we mean when we talk about environmental sustainability. As more and more people become aware of the full extent to which corporations and individuals may harm the environment, this is becoming an increasingly pressing issue. Making ethical choices that lessen your company's detrimental effect on the environment is what we mean when we talk about environmental sustainability. The focus here is on creating systems that will allow companies to become fully sustainable in the long run, rather than just cutting down on energy use and trash.

Theoretical Review

The theory of affordance and diffusion of innovation theory was used for this study. Therefore, the underpinning theory for this study is the theory of affordance theory.

Theory of Affordance

Affordance theory, originally proposed by psychologist James J. Gibson, describes the potential actions that an environment or object affords an individual. In other words, it is about the possibilities for action provided by the environment relative to the individual's capabilities. Affordances are perceived directly and are intrinsically linked to the functional properties of the environment or objects within it.

In the context of information systems and business intelligence (BI), affordance theory can be used to understand how technological tools and systems offer potential actions and opportunities for users within an organization. This perspective helps explain how the use of BI tools can lead to better decision-making and enhanced sustainability practices in organizations. In the realm of Business Intelligence, affordance theory can be applied to understand how BI tools and systems provide various possibilities for action to enhance decision-making and operational efficiency.

Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DOI)

French sociologist Gabriel Tarde first proposed this idea in 1903, and it was Everett Rogers who brought it to a wider audience in 1971. It contends that technical competence is not the only factor in creativity or creation, but that teamwork plays an equally important role. How a certain group of people, defined by their characteristics and socioeconomic status, perceives a new technical development is highly context dependent. The notion suggests categorizing potential buyers according to their current needs, and it encourages inventors to do the same when marketing new products. To put it another way, the inventor has to know who they're selling to in order for their commercialization efforts to be successful (Sartipi, 2020).

This theory delves into the process of innovation and technology adoption in companies by outlining a three-step process: assessment, decision-making, and implementation. It aims to help businesses reap the advantages of these advancements (Paradza & Daramola, 2021).

The DOI theory can be applied to understand how BI tools and systems are adopted within organizations and their impact on achieving sustainability. By understanding and applying the principles of DOI theory, organizations can effectively promote the adoption of BI technologies and practices that drive sustainability, ensuring long-term success and competitiveness in their industry

Empirical Reviews

Alm and Malmberg's (2022) investigates the role of data integration and collection, data or analysis driven strategy, predictive analytics, dashboards, and

visualizations. The findings demonstrate that organisations have a good outlook on BI&A for sustainability, but they do have certain cautions to keep in mind to make sure it works for their sustainability initiatives.

The impact of business intelligence systems and knowledge management on the sustainability performance of Algeria's tourist sector was investigated by Menaouer, Mohammed, and Nada (2022). The research found that knowledge management techniques correlate positively with sustainability performance. Sustainability performance was also positively affected by the business intelligence components.

Using data collected from nine different Jordanian pharmaceutical industrial enterprises based in Amman, Altarawneh (2024) sought to determine how business intelligence affects the sustainability of entrepreneurial ventures. The study found a strong correlation between business intelligence and dimensions of business sustainable entrepreneurship, and its most important finding is that business intelligence has a statistically significant effect on business sustainable entrepreneurship at the 0.05 level of significance.

Cheng, Singh, Zhang, and Wang (2023) examined factors that influence manufacturing organisations' sustainability performance took green knowledge management into account as a moderator. They also looked at the effect of business intelligence and big data analytics capabilities on performance. Findings showed that business intelligence was shown to be the key aspect influencing big data analytics capabilities, with sustainability performance being the positive effect of this capability.

METHODOLOGY

The researcher employed a cross-sectional survey, a type of quasi-experimental design, since the study elements were beyond the researcher's control. This design was chosen as it aligns with the descriptive nature of the study. The population of this study comprise of management staffs selected from ten (10) different financial institutions in Rivers State ranging from deposit money banks, insurance firms, and micro finance banks. The accessible population comprise of one hundred and thirty-five (135) management staff selected from deposit money banks, insurance firms, and micro finance banks. The samples were selected using a random sampling procedure. One hundred and one (101), drawn from the population, while the sample size was determined using the Taro Yamane's method. A well-structured questionnaire was used to gather data for this investigation. There was a total of one hundred and one (101) questionnaires issued to participants; however, only eighty-one (81) were actually collected and used for the research. The Pearson Moment Correlation Coefficient

was used to test the hypotheses for this investigation.

Demographic Characteristics

Variable	Category	Percentage	Frequency
Gender	Male	48	59.3
	Female	33	40.7
Age	31 - 40 years	20	24.7
	41 - 50 year	32	39.5
	51 year and above	29	35.8
Career level	Upper management	33	40.7
	Middle management	48	59.2
Qualification	Bachelor's degree	36	44.4
	Post graduate degree	45	55.6
work experience	Less or 5 years	17	21.0
	6 - 10 year	24	29.6
	11 and above	40	47.4
Marital Status	Single	28	34.6
	Married	53	65.4

Source: Researcher (2025)

This table provides a snapshot of the demographic characteristics of a particular group, likely a workforce or professional organization. The analysis in the table above reveals that the majority of respondents were male (59.3%) and primarily aged between 41 and 50 years (39.5%). Most participants held middle management positions (59.2%) and had postgraduate qualifications (55.6%). Additionally, a significant portion had over 11 years of experience in their respective fields (47.4%), and the majority were married (65.4%). These findings suggest that the respondents were well-qualified to answer the questionnaire and contributed meaningfully to achieving the study's objectives.

Test of Hypotheses

This study employed the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient to test the hypotheses, using a 95% confidence interval. The decision criterion was established such that a p-value greater than 0.05 ($p > 0.05$) indicated acceptance of the null hypothesis, while a p-value less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) led to its rejection.

The relationship between data warehousing and environmental sustainability of financial institutions in Nigeria.

Correlation			
		Data warehousing	Environmental Sustainability
Data Warehousing	Pearson Correlation	1	.854**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	81	81

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output v22.0, (2024)

The correlation coefficient is 0.854 which indicates a strong positive correlation between Data Warehousing and Environmental Sustainability. The p-value (significance) is 0.000. This extremely low p-value indicates a very high level of statistical significance. In essence, the analysis reveals a strong, positive, and statistically significant relationship between Data Warehousing and Environmental Sustainability of

financial institutions in Nigeria. This implies that these two factors are closely related, and changes in one tend to be associated with changes in the other.

Relationship between data visualization and environmental sustainability of financial institutions in Nigeria.

Correlation			
		Data Visualization	Environmental Sustainability
Data Visualization	Pearson Correlation	1	.789**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	81	81

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output v22.0, (2024)

This correlation table highlights a statistically significant relationship between "Data Visualization" and "Environmental Sustainability. The Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.789 indicates a strong positive linear relationship. This means that there's a tendency for "Data Visualization" and "Environmental Sustainability" to move in the same direction. The "Sig. (2-tailed)" value of 0.000 (or very close to zero) signifies that this correlation is extremely unlikely to have occurred by random chance. this data suggests that there's a strong and reliable link between how data is visualized and the level of environmental sustainability of financial institutions in Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study investigated the association between business intelligence (BI) components—data warehouse and data visualization—and the environmental sustainability of financial institutions in Nigeria. The hypotheses posited that there would be no significant relationship between these BI components and environmental sustainability. However, the findings contradicted these hypotheses, revealing significant relationships. The findings revealed a strong positive correlation between data warehousing and the environmental sustainability of financial institutions. As centralized repositories integrating data from multiple sources, data warehouses offer a holistic view of an organization's information. Additionally, the study identified a significant positive relationship between data visualization and the environmental sustainability of financial institutions in Nigeria. Data visualization, the process of combining data from different sources into a coherent dataset. The significant relationships between BI components and environmental sustainability highlight the importance of investing in BI technologies and practices. Financial institutions in Nigeria and beyond can benefit from adopting advanced data warehousing and data visualization. These investments not only enhance operational efficiency and decision-making but also position institutions for long-term environmental sustainability. The findings correlate with Alm and Malmberg (2022); Menaouer, Mohammed and Nada (2022); Altarawneh (2024); Cheng, Singh, Singh, Zhang and Wang, (2023).

CONCLUSION

The study explored the link between business intelligence (BI) components—specifically data warehouse and data visualization—and the environmental sustainability of financial institutions in Nigeria. Findings suggest a significant relationship between data warehouse and data visualization with environmental sustainability. This indicates that the effective implementation and utilization

of data warehouses and data visualization strategies contribute positively to the environmental sustainability of financial institutions in Nigeria. The significant relationship observed suggests that financial institutions that invest in robust BI frameworks, particularly in data warehousing and visualization, are better positioned to achieve environmental sustainability. These institutions can leverage accurate, timely, and integrated data to make informed decisions, optimize operations, reduce costs, and ultimately enhance their financial performance and stability.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Financial institutions in Rivers State should prioritize investment in advanced data warehousing technologies. This includes upgrading existing data warehouse systems to more sophisticated platforms that offer better data storage, retrieval, and analysis capabilities. By doing so, these institutions can ensure that they have a solid foundation for comprehensive data management, which is crucial for strategic decision-making and long-term economic sustainability.
2. Financial institutions should implement advanced data visualization tools to simplify complex data sets into clear and comprehensible visual representations. Efficient data visualization enables decision-makers to quickly interpret key insights on environmental sustainability, including resource usage trends, carbon emissions, and waste management practices. Interactive dashboards and real-time visual analytics can drive informed decision-making and foster a culture of sustainability within the organization. Training staff to effectively use these tools can further amplify their impact, ensuring that all levels of the organization are aligned with sustainability goals.

Contribution to Knowledge

- **Empirical Evidence on Business Intelligence and Sustainability:** This study provides empirical validation that business intelligence components, specifically data warehousing and data visualization, have a significant relationship with environmental sustainability in financial institutions in Nigeria. This reinforces the growing role of data-driven decision-making in achieving sustainability goals.
- **Advancing Business Intelligence Research in Sustainability:** While business intelligence is traditionally associated with operational efficiency and profitability, this study expands its application to environmental sustainability, offering new insights into how financial institutions can leverage data-driven strategies for sustainability initiatives.
- **Context-Specific Insights for Nigerian Financial Institutions:** Given the limited research on business

- intelligence and sustainability in the Nigerian financial sector, this study fills a critical gap by providing localized insights into how data-driven tools contribute to environmental sustainability efforts in developing economies.
- **Strategic Implications for Financial Institutions:** The findings provide practical insights for financial institutions in Nigeria, showing that adopting **advanced data management techniques** can drive sustainability. Banks and other financial institutions can optimize resource use, reduce environmental impact, and align their strategies with global sustainability standards.
- **Framework for Future Research:** The study lays a foundation for future research on the broader impact of business intelligence on sustainability, encouraging further exploration of other business intelligence dimensions such as data integration and data mining in relation to environmental and economic sustainability.

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